

A Physics-Informed Neural Network with a Modified Lorentzian Activation for Nonlocal Gradient-Flow Equations in Dynamic Density Functional Theory

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Abstract

We develop a physics-informed neural network (PINN) framework for nonlocal partial differential equations arising in dynamic density functional theory. Such equations are challenging for standard PINN methods because they combine nonlinearities, nonlocal interaction terms, and an underlying gradient-flow structure, often leading to slow convergence and difficult optimization. To address these issues, we introduce a PINN formulation based on a modified Lorentzian activation function. The method is tested on four examples in one and two space dimensions. In the first example, the exact stationary solution is known, while in the remaining cases the neural-network approximations are validated against reference solutions computed using continuous and discontinuous Galerkin finite element discretizations. Accuracy and physical consistency are assessed through L^1 , L^2 , and L^∞ errors, together with mass conservation and energy dissipation. The results show that the proposed activation accelerates convergence relative to the standard tanh activation while maintaining good agreement with the reference dynamics. These findings suggest that the proposed framework is a promising machine-learning approach for the simulation of nonlocal gradient-flow phenomena.

Nomenclature

$\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$	=	spatial domain,
$\partial\Omega$	=	boundary of the domain,
\mathbf{n}	=	outward unit normal on $\partial\Omega$,
$\rho(\mathbf{x}, t)$	=	density,
$\rho_0(\mathbf{x})$	=	initial density,
$\rho_\theta(\mathbf{x}, t)$	=	neural-network approximation of the density,
θ	=	neural-network parameter vector,
$\mu = \delta\mathcal{E}/\delta\rho$	=	chemical potential,
$E[\rho]$	=	free-energy functional,
$\mathcal{D}(\rho)$	=	energy-dissipation functional,
$H(\rho)$	=	local free-energy density,
$V(\mathbf{x})$	=	prescribed confining potential,
$W(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$	=	interaction kernel,
$W * \rho$	=	spatial convolution of W and ρ ,
k_B	=	Boltzmann constant.

Abbreviations

PINN	=	physics-informed neural network,
PDE	=	partial differential equation,
DFT	=	density functional theory,
DDFT	=	dynamic density functional theory,
FEM	=	finite element method,
CG	=	continuous Galerkin,
DG	=	discontinuous Galerkin.

1 Introduction

Gradient-flow partial differential equations form an important class of models for dissipative systems, including linear and nonlinear diffusion, aggregation, and nonlocal interaction dynamics [1, 2, 3]. Within this framework, dynamic density functional theory (DDFT) provides a continuum description for the evolution of interacting particle densities through a free-energy-driven formulation rooted in classical density functional theory [4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. DDFT and related density-functional approaches have been used to study a broad range of physical phenomena, including colloidal fluids [5, 6, 7], phase separation [9], wetting and interfacial dynamics [10, 11], confined systems [12], and nucleation processes [13].

Despite this appealing variational structure, DDFT-type gradient-flow equations remain numerically challenging. The interplay of nonlinearities, nonlocal interaction operators, and external potentials gives rise to complex multiscale solution behaviour, while the underlying gradient-flow structure imposes fundamental physical constraints, notably mass conservation and free-energy dissipation. Consequently, numerical approximations must achieve not only accuracy but also preserve these essential physical properties. This has led to the development of structure-preserving finite-volume, finite-element, and discontinuous Galerkin methods for nonlinear and nonlocal gradient-flow problems, with particular emphasis on preserving positivity and ensuring discrete energy decay [14, 15, 16, 17]. Although such methods provide reliable numerical approximations, their implementation can become technically demanding in more complex settings, thereby prompting the exploration of alternative computational approaches.

Physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) have emerged as a flexible framework for the numerical solution of differential equations by embedding governing equations, boundary conditions, and initial data directly into the training objective [18, 19, 20]. Their mesh-free formulation and reliance on automatic differentiation have led to a wide range of extensions, including variational and finite-element-inspired formulations [21], finite-element-trained neural methods [22], time-discrete Runge–Kutta-based approaches [23], and methods for nonlocal and integro-differential equations [24, 25]. Despite these advances, applying PINNs to DDFT-type gradient-flow equations remains challenging, particularly in the presence of nonlinear and nonlocal effects and the need to capture the underlying dissipative structure.

In this work, we propose a PINN framework for nonlocal PDEs arising in DDFT, with particular focus on the effect of the activation function on convergence and approximation quality. The main novelty of the approach is the introduction of a modified Lorentzian activation, designed to improve the approximation and optimization of nonlinear and nonlocal gradient-flow problems. The framework is tested on four examples in one and two space dimensions: a nonlocal interaction problem with a known stationary solution, a nonlinear diffusion problem in a double-well potential, a nonlinear diffusion problem with nonlocal attractive interactions, and a two-dimensional droplet coalescence problem. For all four examples, the neural-network solutions are compared with reference solutions computed using continuous Galerkin (CG) and discontinuous Galerkin (DG) finite element methods (FEM). The assessment includes L^1 , L^2 , and L^∞ errors, together with diagnostic plots for mass conservation and free-energy dissipation. Our numerical results show that the proposed activation yields faster convergence than the standard \tanh activation while maintaining close agreement with the reference solutions.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the class of nonlocal gradient-flow equations considered in this work and recalls the corresponding free-energy structure. Section 3 presents the PINN formulation and the associated loss functional. Section 4 describes the practical implementation, including the modified Lorentzian activation, the discrete residual approximation, and the training procedure. Section 5 reports the numerical results and compares the proposed approach with FEM and DG reference solutions. Section 6 closes the paper. For completeness, the appendices collect supplementary numerical details used in the paper. Appendix A summarizes the discrete treatment of the nonlocal interaction term, while Appendix B outlines the finite-element discretizations used to compute the reference solutions.

2 Gradient flow for nonlinear diffusion

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ with $d \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ be a bounded domain with Lipschitz boundary $\partial\Omega$ and outward unit normal \mathbf{n} . We consider a nonlinear diffusion equation in Wasserstein gradient-flow form for a nonnegative density $\rho : \Omega \times [0, T] \rightarrow [0, \infty)$. Given $T > 0$, we seek ρ satisfying

$$\partial_t \rho - \nabla \cdot (\rho \nabla \mu) = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \times (0, T], \quad (1)$$

where $\mu := \delta\mathcal{E}/\delta\rho$ denotes the variational derivative of the free energy. We impose the no-flux boundary condition

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot (\rho \nabla \mu) = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega \times (0, T], \quad (2)$$

which prevents mass transfer across $\partial\Omega$ and ensures the conservation of the total mass $\int_{\Omega} \rho \, d\mathbf{x}$. The initial condition is

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \rho_0(\mathbf{x}) \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (3)$$

where ρ_0 is smooth and strictly positive [26].

The free energy is

$$\mathcal{E}(\rho) = \int_{\Omega} H(\rho) \, d\mathbf{x} + \int_{\Omega} V(\mathbf{x}) \rho \, d\mathbf{x} + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} (W * \rho)(\mathbf{x}) \rho(\mathbf{x}) \, d\mathbf{x}. \quad (4)$$

Here $H(\rho)$ is a local entropic term, $V(\mathbf{x})$ is a prescribed confining potential, and $W * \rho$ accounts for nonlocal interactions through the spatial convolution

$$(W * \rho)(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int_{\Omega} W(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \rho(\mathbf{y}, t) \, d\mathbf{y}. \quad (5)$$

Assuming sufficient regularity, the variational derivative can be written explicitly as

$$\mu := \frac{\delta\mathcal{E}}{\delta\rho} = H'(\rho) + V + (W * \rho). \quad (6)$$

Substituting (6) into (1) yields the equivalent form

$$\partial_t \rho = \nabla \cdot \left(\rho \nabla [H'(\rho) + V + W * \rho] \right). \quad (7)$$

We assume $H \in C^1((0, \infty)) \cap C([0, \infty))$ is convex, $V \in C^1(\bar{\Omega})$, and $W \in C^1(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is symmetric in the sense that $W(-\mathbf{z}) = W(\mathbf{z})$ for all $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^d$. The factor ρ in the flux plays the role of the mobility in the Wasserstein gradient-flow formulation. Since this mobility vanishes when $\rho = 0$, the equation may be degenerate in low-density regions, which can affect the regularity theory and well-posedness properties of the problem.

For smooth solutions of (7) satisfying (2), the free energy dissipates according to

$$\frac{d}{dt} E[\rho(t)] = -\mathcal{D}(\rho(t)), \quad \mathcal{D}(\rho) := \int_{\Omega} \rho \left| \nabla \frac{\delta E}{\delta \rho} \right|^2 \, d\mathbf{x} \geq 0, \quad (8)$$

so that $\mathcal{E}(\rho(t))$ is non-increasing in time, while (2) ensures mass conservation.

The class of equations considered above includes important models arising in dynamic density functional theory. In particular, for suitable choices of the local free-energy density H , the confining potential V , and the interaction kernel W , equation (7) recovers the standard overdamped DDFT evolution for interacting Brownian particles. Such formulations are well established in the DDFT literature; see, for example, [9, 27, 7, 12]. The framework developed here therefore applies both to general nonlocal gradient-flow problems and, more specifically, to the DDFT-type models considered in the numerical experiments below.

3 Neural network formulation

In the PINN framework, we assume that the solution ρ lies in the parametric family $\mathcal{N} = \{\rho_{\theta} : \theta \in \Theta\}$ and estimate the parameter vector θ by minimizing an L^2 empirical objective built from the PDE residual together with the initial and boundary conditions [20, 28]. From a statistical perspective, this corresponds to empirical risk minimization over the finite-dimensional parameter space Θ .

We take ρ_{θ} to be a fully connected feedforward neural network with input dimension d_1 , hidden widths d_2, \dots, d_L , output dimension d_{L+1} , and L affine transformations, defined by the composition

$$\rho_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}, t) = (C_L \circ \sigma \circ C_{L-1} \circ \dots \circ \sigma \circ C_1)(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (9)$$

where σ is an activation function applied componentwise. The maps $C_k : \mathbb{R}^{d_k} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d_{k+1}}$ are affine and given by

$$C_k(\mathbf{z}) = W_k \mathbf{z} + \mathbf{b}_k, \quad W_k \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{k+1} \times d_k}, \quad \mathbf{b}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{k+1}}, \quad (10)$$

so that the parameter vector is $\theta = \{W_k, \mathbf{b}_k\}_{k=1}^L$, whose dimension is

$$\dim(\theta) = \sum_{k=1}^L d_{k+1}(d_k + 1). \quad (11)$$

If the activation function σ is smooth, then the neural-network representation inherits the corresponding regularity. In practice, we require ρ_θ to be differentiable with respect to \mathbf{x} and t so that the PDE residual can be evaluated by automatic differentiation [29].

As in standard PINN formulations, we train ρ_θ by minimizing a composite loss built from terms associated with the governing equation, the initial data, and the boundary condition. The precise form of the residual and the relative weighting of the loss terms may vary across applications and problem classes [20, 28]. For the present model, we adopt the strong-form residual

$$r(\rho)(\mathbf{x}, t) := \partial_t \rho(\mathbf{x}, t) - \nabla \cdot (\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) \nabla \mu(\mathbf{x}, t)), \quad (12)$$

and define the loss functional by

$$\mathcal{L}(\rho) := \lambda_{\text{pde}} \int_0^T \int_\Omega |r(\rho)(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2 \, d\mathbf{x} \, dt + \lambda_{\text{ic}} \int_\Omega |\rho(\mathbf{x}, 0) - \rho_0(\mathbf{x})|^2 \, d\mathbf{x} + \lambda_{\text{bc}} \int_0^T \int_{\partial\Omega} \left| \mathbf{n} \cdot \left(\rho \nabla \frac{\delta \mathcal{E}[\rho]}{\delta \rho} \right) \right|^2 \, dS \, dt. \quad (13)$$

Here, the loss functional \mathcal{L} consists of three weighted contributions, with positive coefficients $\lambda_{\text{pde}}, \lambda_{\text{ic}}, \lambda_{\text{bc}}$ controlling their relative importance. The first term penalizes the PDE's residual in the interior of the space–time domain, the second term enforces fidelity to the initial condition, and the third term penalizes violations of the boundary condition via the normal flux on $\partial\Omega$. Since these three terms typically differ in scale, the weights balance their contributions and thus influence both convergence and the quality of the final approximation.

Having defined the loss functional \mathcal{L} , we now consider its minimization over the trial set of neural-network approximations

$$V_N := \{ \rho_\theta : \Omega \times [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid \theta \in \Theta \},$$

that is,

$$\min_{\rho \in V_N} \mathcal{L}(\rho).$$

Since the trial set V_N is parameterized by the neural-network parameters, this problem is written as the finite-dimensional optimization problem

$$\min_{\theta \in \Theta} \mathcal{L}(\rho_\theta).$$

This is, in general, a nonconvex optimization problem in θ . In practice, the problem is solved approximately by first-order stochastic optimization methods, with the aim of identifying a parameter vector θ for which the PDE residual, the initial-condition residual, and the boundary-condition residual are all simultaneously minimized. Moreover, because the integrals in \mathcal{L} are generally not available in closed form, they are approximated numerically, which yields a computable discrete loss. The resulting discrete formulation is described in Section 4.

4 Implementation

4.1 Implementation of the neural network

This section presents the concrete architecture and numerical realization of the neural-network formulation introduced in Sections 2 and 3. In particular, we describe the parameterization, the discrete approximations of the chemical potential and residuals, the resulting discrete loss functional, and the optimization procedure used in the computations.

In the implementation, we retain the architecture introduced in Section 3, and denote by g_θ the raw network output before the final output transformation. We choose the following activation function

$$\sigma_\varepsilon(z) = z \frac{\varepsilon^2}{z^2 + \varepsilon^2},$$

the raw output is written as

$$g_\theta(\mathbf{x}, t) = (C_L \circ \sigma_\varepsilon \circ C_{L-1} \circ \cdots \circ \sigma_\varepsilon \circ C_1)(\mathbf{x}, t),$$

with affine maps

$$C_k(\mathbf{z}) = W_k \mathbf{z} + \mathbf{b}_k,$$

and parameter vector

$$\theta = \{W_k, \mathbf{b}_k\}_{k=1}^L.$$

A key contribution of this work is the introduction of the Lorentzian rational activation. Figure 1 illustrates its behavior near the origin and its localized profile in comparison with $\tanh(z)$. Analytically, this activation has two characteristic regimes. For $|z| \ll \varepsilon$, one has $\sigma_\varepsilon(z) \approx z$, so the activation is approximately linear near the origin. For $|z| \gg \varepsilon$, one has $\sigma_\varepsilon(z) \approx \varepsilon^2/z$, so the activation decreases and suppresses large input magnitudes. Hence, σ_ε combines near-origin linearity with attenuation of large-amplitude inputs. In the numerical experiments, replacing \tanh by σ_ε leads to faster convergence and often to fewer optimization steps for a fixed target accuracy, although each iteration is slightly more expensive computationally.

Figure 1: Activation profile of $\sigma_{0.06}(z)$. Left: zoom near the origin. Right: comparison with $\tanh(z)$ on a wider interval.

The final density approximation is obtained by applying an output map \mathcal{T} to the raw output g_θ . In other words,

$$\rho_\theta(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathcal{T}(g_\theta(\mathbf{x}, t)),$$

with

$$\mathcal{T}(z) = \begin{cases} z, & \text{identity,} \\ z^2, & \text{quadratic,} \\ \log(1 + e^z), & \text{softplus.} \end{cases}$$

In practice, the identity map is sufficient in regimes where training remains stable and the learned solution remains nonnegative over the domain. However, during the early stages of training the raw output $g_\theta(\mathbf{x}, t)$ may transiently become negative before the parameters approach a physically admissible solution. This may violate the constraint $\rho \geq 0$ and lead to numerical instabilities in the evaluation of the residual. In such cases, we instead use a nonnegative output map, namely the softplus or quadratic transformation, to improve robustness.

To construct a discrete counterpart of the chemical potential (6) and the residual (12), we discretize the spatial domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ on a structured Cartesian grid with nodes $\{\mathbf{x}_i\}_{i=1}^N \subset \Omega$, where each $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$, and sample time collocation points $\{t_k\}_{k=1}^K \subset [0, T]$ independently from the uniform distribution $\mathcal{U}(0, T)$.

For each sampled time t_k , we collect the nodal values of the density approximation into the vector

$$\boldsymbol{\rho}_\theta(t_k) = (\rho_\theta(\mathbf{x}_1, t_k), \dots, \rho_\theta(\mathbf{x}_N, t_k))^\top.$$

The nonlocal interaction term in (6) is then approximated using a precomputed convolution operator $\Phi \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ through

$$(W * \rho_\theta)(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k) \approx (\Phi \boldsymbol{\rho}_\theta(t_k))_i,$$

during both training and evaluation. The construction of Φ and its relation to the interaction kernel W are described in Appendix A.

Accordingly, the discrete chemical potential at grid nodes \mathbf{x}_i and times t_k is defined by

$$\mu_\theta(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k) = H'(\rho_\theta(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k)) + V(\mathbf{x}_i) + (\Phi \boldsymbol{\rho}_\theta(t_k))_i.$$

Using this discrete chemical potential, we define the residual enforced at spatial nodes \mathbf{x}_i and times t_k by

$$r_h(\rho_\theta)(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k) := \partial_t \rho_\theta(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k) - \nabla_h \cdot (\rho_\theta(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k) \nabla_h \mu_\theta(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k)).$$

The no-flux boundary residual on $\partial\Omega_h \times \{t_k\}$ is defined by

$$b_h(\rho_\theta)(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k) := \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x}_i) \cdot J_h(\rho_\theta)(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k), \quad \mathbf{x}_i \in \partial\Omega_h,$$

where $J_h(\rho_\theta)$ denotes the discrete approximation of the flux $\rho_\theta \nabla \mu_\theta$ used in the residual evaluation. The initial-condition residual is enforced at the spatial grid nodes on the initial time slice $t = 0$ by

$$c_h(\rho_\theta)(\mathbf{x}_i) := \rho_\theta(\mathbf{x}_i, 0) - \rho_0(\mathbf{x}_i).$$

In the discrete residuals above, the temporal derivative $\partial_t \rho_\theta$ appearing in r_h is computed by automatic differentiation with respect to t , while the spatial derivatives entering both r_h and the boundary flux J_h are approximated by finite differences. More precisely, spatial derivatives are approximated by second-order centred finite differences in the interior together with second-order one-sided boundary stencils at the boundary, and the discrete divergence ∇_h is implemented in flux form using the same family of stencils.

The three terms of the loss functional (13) are approximated by empirical averages over the spatial grid and sampled times. In practice, we further augment the resulting discrete objective by an additional mass-penalty term in order to improve conservation of the total mass during training. The discrete training objective therefore takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_h(\theta) = & \lambda_{\text{pde}} \frac{1}{KN} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{i=1}^N |r_h(\rho_\theta)(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k)|^2 + \lambda_{\text{ic}} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\rho_\theta(\mathbf{x}_i, 0) - \rho_0(\mathbf{x}_i)|^2 \\ & + \lambda_{\text{bc}} \frac{1}{K|\partial\Omega_h|} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\mathbf{x}_i \in \partial\Omega_h} |b_h(\rho_\theta)(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k)|^2 + \lambda_{\text{mass}} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \left| \sum_{i=1}^N \rho_\theta(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k) \Delta V - M_0 \right|^2. \end{aligned}$$

Here, $|\partial\Omega_h|$ denotes the number of boundary nodes, ΔV is the grid-cell volume element, and

$$M_0 = \int_{\Omega} \rho_0 d\mathbf{x}$$

is the prescribed total initial mass.

We minimize $\mathcal{L}_h(\theta)$ using the Adam optimizer. To evaluate the discrete loss at each iteration, we sample only in time and retain the full Cartesian spatial grid. Accordingly, we draw a mini-batch of K independent time points

$$\mathbf{t} = (t_1, \dots, t_K)^\top, \quad t_k \stackrel{\text{i.i.d.}}{\sim} \mathcal{U}(0, T).$$

For each sampled time, the network is evaluated at all spatial grid nodes, producing a batch of density fields

$$R_k(\mathbf{x}_i) = \rho_\theta(\mathbf{x}_i, t_k), \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad k = 1, \dots, K.$$

These values are naturally arranged as a tensor $R \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times n_1 \times \dots \times n_d}$, where n_1, \dots, n_d are the numbers of grid points in each spatial direction. This tensor representation is then used to assemble the discrete residual, boundary, and mass terms entering $\mathcal{L}_h(\theta)$.

4.2 Reference finite element solvers

To assess the accuracy of the neural-network solutions, we compute reference solutions using finite element discretizations implemented in FEniCS [30, 31]. In the present work, such reference computations are carried out for the one- and two-dimensional test cases only. In all test cases, the reference computations use the same initial data, model parameters, and boundary conditions as the neural-network experiments, ensuring direct comparability.

For one-dimensional domains, we use a discontinuous Galerkin discretization with piecewise linear elements on structured meshes [32, 33]. Local conservation is enforced through numerical fluxes at element interfaces, and a minmod slope limiter [34] is applied after each solve to control spurious oscillations. The nonlocal interaction term is treated using the same discrete convolution operator described in Appendix A, so that the comparison isolates the effect of the solution strategy rather than the nonlocal discretization itself. Time integration is performed with a semi-implicit Crank–Nicolson scheme, and the nonlinear systems arising at each time step are solved by Newton’s method using automatic differentiation within FEniCS/UFL.

For two-dimensional domains, we use continuous Lagrange finite elements on triangular meshes, together with the same treatment of the nonlocal term, the same nonlinear solver framework, and the same temporal discretization. The accuracy of the neural-network solutions is then assessed against these reference solutions using L^2 and L^∞ error norms at selected time points. For completeness, the weak formulations and reference discretizations used in Section 5 are summarized in Appendix B.

5 Numerical results

In this section, we present a series of numerical experiments designed to assess the accuracy and qualitative performance of the proposed method across a range of gradient-flow and DDFT-type problems. The tests include cases with known equilibrium states, which allow direct validation against exact solutions, as well as more challenging interacting-particle configurations involving nonlocal attraction, excluded-volume effects, and wall-induced wetting. Our goal is to examine whether the method correctly reproduces the expected transient dynamics, captures the relevant steady or metastable structures, and preserves the underlying free-energy dissipation mechanism. The numerical experiments were carried out on a laptop equipped with an NVIDIA RTX 3500 Ada Generation Laptop GPU.

5.1 Example 1: nonlocal interaction test

As a first test, we consider a one-dimensional model in which the free energy contains only the nonlocal interaction contribution, with interaction kernel

$$W(x) = \frac{1}{2}|x|^2 - \log|x|,$$

while the internal energy contribution and the external potential are both absent, that is,

$$H(\rho) = 0, \quad V(x) = 0.$$

For this choice of interaction kernel, the unique stationary solution of unit mass is known explicitly; see, for instance, [15], and is given by

$$\rho_\infty(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\pi}\sqrt{2-x^2}, & |x| \leq \sqrt{2}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The equilibrium profile ρ_∞ is 1/2-Hölder continuous. It is the global minimizer of the free-energy functional (4), and solutions of (1) converge exponentially fast towards this equilibrium; see [?]. In the numerical experiments, we approximate ρ_∞ by solving (1) up to large times from the Gaussian initial condition

$$\rho(x, 0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}}e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}}.$$

For this experiment, the computations are carried out on the domain $\Omega = [-3, 3]$ using a fully connected feedforward network with 4 hidden layers of width 128. The loss weights are set to $\lambda_{\text{pde}} = 1$, $\lambda_{\text{ic}} = 5$, $\lambda_{\text{bc}} = 1$, and $\lambda_{\text{mass}} = 0.01$, and the batch size is 100. The final density is obtained from the raw network output $g_\theta(x, t)$ via the quadratic map. For the modified Lorentzian activation, the parameter ε is set to 0.05. The modified Lorentzian model is trained for 10,000 iterations, while the corresponding **tanh** model is trained for 30,000 iterations.

Figure 2 compares the loss curves during training and the final steady-state approximations obtained with the modified Lorentzian and standard **tanh** activations on a uniform mesh with grid size $\Delta x = 0.01$. Both activations produce numerical profiles in good agreement with the exact stationary solution. However, the modified Lorentzian activation gives a more accurate final approximation. Its L^1 error is of order 10^{-2} and is about a factor of two smaller than that of the **tanh** activation, while the L^∞ error is also smaller.

The main difference, however, lies in the optimization behavior. The **tanh** model reaches a loss of order 10^{-5} only after 30,000 training iterations, whereas the modified Lorentzian activation reaches the same level after about 3,000 iterations. In wall-clock time, **tanh** requires about 532s to reach this tolerance, whereas the modified Lorentzian activation reaches it in about 236s. This corresponds to more than a twofold reduction in training time. Moreover, after 10,000 iterations, the modified Lorentzian activation reaches a lower loss, of order 10^{-6} .

Although each iteration with the modified Lorentzian activation is more expensive, about 3.5 times the cost of one **tanh** iteration on our hardware, its much faster convergence more than compensates for the larger per-iteration cost. Overall, for this test problem, the modified Lorentzian activation provides both improved optimization efficiency and improved final approximation accuracy relative to the standard **tanh** baseline. In the remainder of the numerical experiments, we therefore use the modified Lorentzian activation.

(a) Training loss for the modified Lorentzian activation.

(b) Modified Lorentzian PINN vs exact solution.

(d) `tanh` PINN vs exact solution.

Figure 2: Comparison of the modified Lorentzian and standard `tanh` activations. Panels (a) and (c) show the loss curves during training, while panels (b) and (d) compare the final steady-state approximations with the exact stationary solution.

5.2 Example 2: nonlinear diffusion with a double-well potential

We next consider a one-dimensional nonlinear diffusion problem with a double-well external potential, following the benchmark introduced in [15]. The governing equation is

$$\partial_t \rho = \partial_x (\rho \partial_x (\nu \rho^{m-1} + V(x))), \quad V(x) = \frac{x^4}{4} - \frac{x^2}{2},$$

posed on the domain $\Omega = [-3, 3]$ up to the final time $T = 4$. This test is of interest because the double-well potential drives an initially centered density towards a symmetric bimodal equilibrium localized near the minima of the external potential.

In this experiment, we set $\nu = 1$ and $m = 2$, and take a Gaussian density as the initial condition

$$\rho_0(x) = \frac{M}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}\right),$$

with $M = 0.1$ and variance $\sigma^2 = 0.2$. The corresponding free energy is

$$E[\rho] = \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{1}{2}\rho^2 + V(x)\rho\right) dx,$$

and ρ_{∞} denotes the associated equilibrium density.

For this experiment, the loss weights are set to $\lambda_{\text{pde}} = 1$, $\lambda_{\text{ic}} = 1$, $\lambda_{\text{bc}} = 1$, and $\lambda_{\text{mass}} = 0.01$. The neural-network approximation uses a fully connected feedforward architecture with four hidden layers of width 128, as described in Section 4. The modified Lorentzian activation is used with parameter $\varepsilon = 0.05$. The final density is obtained from the raw network output via the identity map. Training is performed for 50,000 iterations. Here, $\rho_{\text{ref}} := \rho_{\text{DG}}$ denotes the reference solution.

The neural-network approximation is compared with the reference solution over the full time horizon. The resulting space-time errors are small, indicating good agreement throughout the simulated interval. In particular, the $L^2(0, T; L^2(\Omega))$ error, defined by integration in both space and time, and the corresponding $L^1(0, T; L^1(\Omega))$ error are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \|\rho_{\text{ref}}(x, t) - \rho_{\theta}(x, t)\|_{L^2(0, T; L^2(\Omega))} &= 4.42 \times 10^{-3}, \\ \|\rho_{\text{ref}}(x, t) - \rho_{\theta}(x, t)\|_{L^1(0, T; L^1(\Omega))} &= 1.13 \times 10^{-2} \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3 summarizes the numerical results for this example. Panel (a) shows the decay of the training loss during optimization, while panel (b) compares the neural-network approximation and the reference solution at selected times. The initially centered profile splits into a symmetric bimodal density as time approaches equilibrium, and the agreement between the two solutions remains good throughout the simulated interval. Panel (c) reports the time evolution of the L^1 and L^2 errors, which remain small over the full time horizon, although they increase during the transient regime before decreasing slightly near the final time. Panel (d) shows the decay of the free-energy gap $E[\rho] - E[\rho_\infty]$ for both approximations. In both cases, the free energy decreases in time, consistently with the dissipative structure of the problem, although a modest discrepancy in the decay rate is visible at intermediate and late times. Finally, panels (e) and (f) report the evolution of the total mass and the relative mass deviation $(M(t) - M_0)/M_0$, respectively, showing that mass is preserved only approximately, with small oscillatory deviations from the initial value over the simulated time interval.

Figure 3: PINN results for example 2. Top left: training loss. Top right: comparison of the PINN and DG solutions at selected times. Middle left: time evolution of the L^1 and L^2 errors between the PINN and DG solutions. Middle right: decay of the relative energy $E[\rho] - E[\rho_\infty]$. Bottom left: evolution of the total mass. Bottom right: relative mass loss over time.

5.3 Example 3: nonlinear diffusion with nonlocal attractive interactions

We next consider a one-dimensional nonlinear diffusion problem with nonlocal attractive interaction, given by

$$\partial_t \rho = \partial_x (\rho \partial_x (\nu \rho^{m-1} + (W * \rho)(x))), \quad W(x) = -\max(0, 1 - |x|),$$

where the interaction kernel W induces attraction through the convolution term $(W * \rho)(x)$.

In this experiment, we set $m = 3$ and $\nu = 1$, and perform the computations on the domain $\Omega = [-3, 3]$ up to the final time $T = 4$. The initial condition is chosen as the characteristic function on $[-1.5, 1.5]$:

$$\rho_0(x) = \frac{1}{4} \chi_{[-1.5, 1.5]}(x).$$

The corresponding free energy is

$$E[\rho] = \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{1}{3} \rho^3 + \frac{1}{2} \rho (W * \rho) \right) dx.$$

This test illustrates the competition between nonlinear diffusion and nonlocal attraction. Starting from a compactly supported piecewise-constant profile, the solution evolves towards a single concentrated peak centered at the origin under the combined effect of diffusion and attraction. Similar aggregation–diffusion test cases were also considered in [17].

For this problem, a single training run over the full time interval did not reliably recover the reference trajectory. To improve stability and accuracy, we therefore adopt a time-window strategy, decomposing the interval $[0, T]$ into four successive equal subintervals and training the network sequentially on each of them. The solution at the end of one window is used to initialize the next. With this strategy, the method tracks the solution trajectory accurately, with each window trained for only 1000 optimization steps. We note, however, that this windowing strategy was not beneficial in the previous test cases, where a single training run over the full time interval produced more accurate results.

For this experiment, the loss weights are set to $\lambda_{\text{pde}} = 1$, $\lambda_{\text{ic}} = 5$, $\lambda_{\text{bc}} = 10^{-3}$, and $\lambda_{\text{mass}} = 0.1$. The neural network is a fully connected feedforward architecture with 6 hidden layers of width 256, using the Lorentzian activation function with $\varepsilon = 0.05$. The final density is obtained from the raw network output $g_{\theta}(y)$ via the identity map. The training is performed with the Adam optimizer using learning rate 10^{-3} and a time-batch size $N_{T,\text{batch}} = 20$.

The neural-network approximation is then compared with the reference solution over the full time horizon. The resulting trajectory errors remain moderate and are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \|\rho_{\text{ref}}(x, t) - \rho_{\theta}(x, t)\|_{L^2(0, T; L^2(\Omega))} &= 3.04 \times 10^{-2}, \\ \|\rho_{\text{ref}}(x, t) - \rho_{\theta}(x, t)\|_{L^1(0, T; L^1(\Omega))} &= 6.83 \times 10^{-2}. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 4 summarizes the numerical results for this example. Panel (a) displays the training loss for the successive time windows used in the computation. Panel (b) compares the neural-network approximation and the reference solution at selected times, and shows how the initially flat, compactly supported function evolves into a single-peaked profile centered at the origin. The agreement is good throughout the simulated time interval. Panel (c) reports the time evolution of the L^1 and L^2 errors between the two solutions. The errors remain moderate over the full time horizon, with visible changes across window boundaries due to the sequential time-window training. Panel (d) shows the decay of the free-energy gap $E[\rho] - E[\rho_{\infty}]$ for both approximations, and in both cases the free energy decreases monotonically in time, consistent with the dissipative structure of the problem, with the two curves remaining in close agreement throughout the simulation. Panels (e) and (f) report the evolution of the total mass and the relative mass deviation, respectively. The jumps visible in these quantities are associated with the transitions between consecutive training windows. Overall, the method captures the aggregation dynamics and the energy decay well, although the windowed training introduces small discontinuities in the error and mass plots.

5.4 Example 4: droplet coalescence without external confinement

We next consider a two-dimensional model for droplet coalescence without external confinement. In contrast to the previous examples, no closed-form equilibrium profile is available. The dynamics are governed entirely by the free-energy structure, with contributions from entropy, short-range repulsion, and attractive interactions. The model is based on the classical density functional theory formulation used, for example, in [35].

In this example, the free energy (4) is specified by

$$H(\rho) = k_B \tau \rho (\ln \rho - 1) + \rho \psi(\rho), \quad V(\mathbf{x}) = 0, \quad W(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \varphi_{\text{attr}}(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|), \quad (14)$$

Figure 4: PINN results for example 3 using a sequential time-window training strategy. Top left: training loss for each time window. Top right: comparison of the neural-network approximation and the DG reference solution at selected times. Middle left: time evolution of the L^1 and L^2 errors between the two solutions. Middle right: decay of the free-energy gap $E[\rho] - E[\rho_\infty]$. Bottom left: evolution of the total mass. Bottom right: relative mass deviation over time.

where τ is the temperature, k_B is the Boltzmann constant and the local repulsive contribution is taken in Carnahan–Starling form [36],

$$\psi(\rho) = k_B \tau \frac{\eta(4 - 3\eta)}{(1 - \eta)^2}, \quad \eta = \frac{\pi \sigma^3 \rho}{6},$$

and the mean-field potential φ_{attr} is defined by

$$\varphi_{\text{attr}}(r) = \begin{cases} 0, & r \leq \sigma, \\ \varphi_{\epsilon, \sigma}^{6-12}(r), & r > \sigma, \end{cases} \quad \varphi_{\epsilon, \sigma}^{6-12}(r) = 4\epsilon \left[-\left(\frac{\sigma}{r}\right)^6 + \left(\frac{\sigma}{r}\right)^{12} \right].$$

The free energy takes the form

$$E(\rho) = \int_{\Omega} [k_B \tau \rho(\mathbf{x})(\ln \rho(\mathbf{x}) - 1) + \rho(\mathbf{x}) \psi(\rho(\mathbf{x}))] d\mathbf{x} + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \rho(\mathbf{x}) \rho(\mathbf{y}) \varphi_{\text{attr}}(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|) d\mathbf{y} d\mathbf{x}.$$

Here the first term is the ideal-gas contribution, the second term represents excess repulsion, and the third term models nonlocal attractive interactions.

With the choice (14), the chemical potential (6) becomes

$$\mu(\mathbf{x}, t) = k_B \tau \ln \rho(\mathbf{x}, t) + \psi(\rho(\mathbf{x}, t)) + \rho(\mathbf{x}, t) \psi'(\rho(\mathbf{x}, t)) + \int_{\Omega} \rho(\mathbf{y}, t) \varphi_{\text{attr}}(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|) d\mathbf{y}.$$

The initial condition is chosen as the smooth union of two diffuse droplets, namely

$$\rho_0(\mathbf{x}) = \rho_g + (\rho_l - \rho_g) s(\mathbf{x}),$$

where ρ_g and ρ_l denote the gas and liquid densities and

$$s(\mathbf{x}) = 1 - (1 - s_1(\mathbf{x}))(1 - s_2(\mathbf{x})),$$

with

$$s_j(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \tanh \left(\frac{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_j| - R_j}{w} \right) \right), \text{ for } j = 1, 2.$$

Here \mathbf{c}_j is the center of droplet j , R_j is its radius, and $w > 0$ controls the interfacial width. In the computations, we take

$$\rho_g = 10^{-3}, \quad \rho_l = 1, \quad \mathbf{c}_1 = (7, 10), \quad \mathbf{c}_2 = (13, 10), \quad R_1 = R_2 = 2, \quad w = 1. \quad (15)$$

Thus, the initial state consists of two nearby diffuse droplets in a low-density background. Under the action of the attractive nonlocal interactions, these structures evolve, merge, and relax toward a single aggregated equilibrium configuration.

For this experiment, the loss weights are chosen as $\lambda_{\text{pde}} = 1$, $\lambda_{\text{ic}} = 10$, and $\lambda_{\text{bc}} = 1$. The neural-network approximation is computed on the domain $\Omega = [0, 20] \times [0, 20]$, using a 40×40 spatial discretization, up to the final time $T = 7$. The temperature is set to 0.4. Training is performed with the Adam optimizer using learning rate 10^{-3} , time mini-batches of size 100, and a total of 10,000 optimization steps. The modified Lorentzian activation is used with parameter $\varepsilon = 0.05$. The final density is obtained from the raw network output $g_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ through the identity map.

Figure 5 summarizes the overall performance of the PINN for the two-dimensional droplet coalescence problem. Panel (a) shows a clear decrease of the training loss, together with persistent fluctuations due to the stochastic nature of mini-batch training. Larger batch sizes may reduce these oscillations, but at a higher memory cost. Panel (b) compares one-dimensional cross-sections at $y = 10$ for several times and shows that the PINN reproduces the FEM reference profiles well, with the largest discrepancy occurring during the transient stage of coalescence. Panel (c) reports the relative L^1 and L^2 errors over time. Both errors remain moderate, but increase gradually during the evolution, indicating that small discrepancies accumulate as the solution progresses toward the merged configuration, before stabilizing as the solution approaches equilibrium. Panel (d) shows the relative mass loss of the PINN solution. Although the mass is not preserved exactly, the deviation remains below 1% over the full time interval.

Figure 6 compares the two-dimensional density fields of the PINN and FEM solutions, together with the absolute error field, at three representative times. At $t = 0$, the PINN reproduces the initial two-droplet configuration accurately, with only very small localized discrepancies near the diffuse interfaces. At $t = 1$, both methods capture the onset of coalescence and the formation of the bridge between the droplets, while the error becomes concentrated along the interfacial region. At $t = 7$, both solutions have relaxed toward a single aggregated droplet, and the remaining discrepancy is again primarily localized near the interface.

The contour plots in Figure 7 confirm the same observations, namely that the agreement is already strong at the initial time, that the largest discrepancies occur during the transient coalescence stage near the bridge region, and that the two solutions come back into closer agreement once the merged droplet approaches equilibrium.

6 Conclusions

In this work, we proposed a physics-informed neural network framework for nonlocal partial differential equations arising in dynamic density functional theory. The method targets gradient-flow problems involving nonlinear diffusion, nonlocal interactions, and physically relevant structural properties such as mass conservation and free-energy dissipation. Its main novelty is the introduction of a modified Lorentzian activation, designed to improve training efficiency and approximation quality in the PINN approximation of nonlinear and nonlocal dynamics.

The proposed framework was tested on one- and two-dimensional benchmark problems, including nonlinear diffusion, aggregation with nonlocal attraction, and droplet coalescence. The

Figure 5: Two-dimensional comparison between the PINN and the FEM reference solution. The figure shows the training loss, one-dimensional cross-sections at $y = 10$, the relative L^1 and L^2 errors over time, and the relative mass loss of the PINN solution.

numerical results showed good agreement with finite element and discontinuous Galerkin reference solutions, both in terms of solution profiles and in terms of qualitative behaviour. In particular, the modified Lorentzian activation consistently led to faster convergence than the standard `tanh` activation in the experiments considered, while maintaining accurate approximations of the reference dynamics. The results also showed that the method can reproduce key physical features of the model, including energy decay and approximate mass conservation.

These findings suggest that PINN methodologies, when combined with suitable activation design, can provide a promising computational approach for nonlocal gradient-flow equations of DDFT type. Since the benchmark problems considered here cover a broad range of behaviours, including local and nonlocal dynamics as well as linear and nonlinear regimes, the proposed activation strategy may also be beneficial for a wider class of PDEs with similar approximation and optimization challenges. At the same time, the present study suggests several directions for further development of the proposed framework, including the treatment of longer time intervals, improved robustness for strongly nonlocal problems, and a more direct incorporation of structural properties into the training procedure. Possible extensions include alternative weak-form formulations and applications to more complex DDFT models and related evolution equations.

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Author contributions

All authors contributed equally to this work.

Figure 6: Two-dimensional density fields for the PINN and FEM solutions, together with the absolute error field, at three representative times. The first, second, and third rows correspond to $t = 0$, $t = 1$, and $t = 7$, respectively.

Figure 7: Contour comparison between the FEM reference solution and the PINN approximation at $t = 0, 1,$ and 7 . Solid lines denote the FEM contours and dashed lines denote the PINN contours. The two contour levels shown correspond to $\rho = 0.1$ and $\rho = 0.5$.

A Appendix: discrete evaluation of the convolution term

This appendix explains how the nonlocal convolution term in (6) is evaluated in the finite-element discretization and how it is reduced to a discrete matrix operation in the implementation.

$$\rho_h(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i \phi_i(x),$$

where $\{\phi_i\}_{i=1}^N$ denotes the basis of the discrete finite-element space. For a given interaction kernel W , the convolution is

$$(W * \rho_h)(y) = \int_{\Omega} W(y-x) \rho_h(x) dx.$$

Evaluating this expression at a node x_k gives

$$(W * \rho_h)(x_k) = \sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i \int_{\Omega} W(x_k - x) \phi_i(x) dx.$$

To obtain a fully discrete representation, we approximate the shifted kernel $W(x_k - x)$ in the same finite-element basis:

$$W(x_k - x) \approx \sum_{m=1}^N B_{mk} \phi_m(x),$$

where B_{mk} are the corresponding interpolation or projection coefficients. Substituting this approximation into the convolution expression yields

$$(W * \rho_h)(x_k) \approx \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N \rho_i B_{mk} \int_{\Omega} \phi_i(x) \phi_m(x) dx.$$

Introducing the mass matrix

$$M_{im} = \int_{\Omega} \phi_i(x) \phi_m(x) dx,$$

we obtain

$$(W * \rho_h)(x_k) \approx \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N \rho_i M_{im} B_{mk}.$$

Since the mass matrix is symmetric, $M_{im} = M_{mi}$, this becomes

$$(W * \rho_h)(x_k) \approx \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N B_{mk} M_{mi} \rho_i = (B^{\top} M \boldsymbol{\rho})_k,$$

where $\boldsymbol{\rho} = (\rho_1, \dots, \rho_N)^{\top}$. Hence, with

$$\Phi = B^{\top} M,$$

the discrete convolution is evaluated through the matrix–vector product $\Phi \boldsymbol{\rho}$.

B Appendix: reference finite element solvers

This appendix summarizes the finite-element reference solvers used in the numerical experiments of Section 5 to generate the solutions against which the neural-network approximations are compared. For completeness, we first recall the weak formulation of (7), which is the standard variational form used as the starting point for finite-element discretization; see, for example, [37, 38].

Starting from (7), we multiply by a test function v and integrate over Ω to obtain the weak formulation

$$\int_{\Omega} \partial_t \rho v \, dx + \int_{\Omega} \rho \nabla \mu \cdot \nabla v \, dx = 0 \quad \forall v \in V,$$

where V is a suitable test space. The boundary contribution vanishes under the no-flux condition $\rho \nabla \mu \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0$ on $\partial\Omega$.

B.1 Continuous Galerkin discretization

We first consider a continuous Galerkin discretization, which approximates the solution by functions that remain continuous across element interfaces. This is the reference method used for the two-dimensional computations in Section 5.

Let $V_h \subset H^1(\Omega)$ be a continuous finite-element space, for example the space of continuous piecewise linear functions on a conforming mesh of Ω . Using a semi-implicit Crank–Nicolson discretization in time, the fully discrete problem is: given $\rho_h^n \in V_h$ at time t^n , find $\rho_h^{n+1} \in V_h$ such that

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\rho_h^{n+1} - \rho_h^n}{\Delta t} v_h \, dx + \int_{\Omega} \rho_h^{n+1/2} \nabla \mu_h^{n+1/2} \cdot \nabla v_h \, dx = 0 \quad \forall v_h \in V_h,$$

where

$$\rho_h^{n+1/2} = \frac{1}{2} (\rho_h^{n+1} + \rho_h^n), \quad \mu_h^{n+1/2} = H'(\rho_h^{n+1/2}) + V + W * \rho_h^n.$$

Here the convolution term is evaluated explicitly at the previous time step,

$$(W * \rho_h^n)(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{\Omega} W(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \rho_h^n(\mathbf{y}) \, d\mathbf{y}.$$

Thus, the local nonlinear terms are treated at the midpoint level, whereas the nonlocal interaction term is treated explicitly. The nonlinear system arising at each time step is solved by Newton iteration, using the Fréchet derivative with respect to ρ_h^{n+1} ; see, for example, [39].

B.2 Discontinuous Galerkin discretization

For the one-dimensional test problems of Section 5, we also consider a discontinuous Galerkin discretization. In this approach, the approximate solution is allowed to be discontinuous across element interfaces, and communication between neighboring elements is enforced through numerical fluxes and jump terms.

Let X_h be a discontinuous finite-element space of piecewise polynomial functions on the mesh. Using the same semi-implicit Crank–Nicolson time discretization, the DG scheme is: given $\rho_h^n \in X_h$, find $\rho_h^{n+1} \in X_h$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \frac{\rho_h^{n+1} - \rho_h^n}{\Delta t} v_h \, dx + \int_{\Omega} \rho_h^{n+1/2} \nabla \mu_h^{n+1/2} \cdot \nabla v_h \, dx \\ - \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}_{\text{int}}} \int_e (\rho_h^{n+1/2} \nabla \mu_h^{n+1/2})^* [v_h] \, ds \\ + 2 \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}_{\text{int}}} \int_e [\rho_h^{n+1/2}] [v_h] \, ds = 0, \quad \forall v_h \in X_h. \end{aligned}$$

Here \mathcal{E}_{int} denotes the set of interior interfaces of the mesh, that is, the boundaries shared by neighboring elements, $[q] = q^+ - q^-$ is the jump of a scalar quantity across an interior interface, and

$$\rho_h^{n+1/2} = \frac{1}{2} (\rho_h^{n+1} + \rho_h^n), \quad \mu_h^{n+1/2} = H'(\rho_h^{n+1/2}) + V + W * \rho_h^n.$$

In one space dimension, the upwind numerical flux is defined by

$$(\rho_h^{n+1/2} \beta_h)^* = \max(\hat{\beta}_h, 0) \rho_h^{n+1/2,-} + \min(\hat{\beta}_h, 0) \rho_h^{n+1/2,+}, \quad \beta_h = \partial_x \mu_h^{n+1/2},$$

where $\hat{\beta}_h$ denotes the average of the traces of β_h across the interface. The last term is a jump stabilization term. As in the continuous Galerkin case, the nonlinear system is solved by Newton iteration. After each time step, a minmod-type slope limiter is applied to reduce spurious oscillations; see [33].

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